

EDUCATION ASSESSMENT METHODS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: This paper explores the significancy and strategies of learning assessment in education. Assessment for learning is quite important aspect in education.

Keywords: *teaching and learning process, learning assessment, English, language, teaching skills, learning process, elf-confidence, self-efficiency.*

Much scholarship has focused on the importance of student assessment in teaching and learning in higher education. Student assessment is a critical aspect of the teaching and learning process. Whether teaching at the undergraduate or graduate level, it is important for instructors to strategically evaluate the effectiveness of their teaching by measuring the extent to which students in the classroom are learning the course material.

Assessment for learners(AFL) is a tool for students to gain the self-confidence and self-efficiency. Teaching is complex; it involves elements such as curriculum, subject matter and epistemology, teaching and learning, and also assessment and evaluation. In other words, the core process of education and schooling engages the nature of what is taught, how that content is taught and learned, and how that teaching/learning is assessed and evaluated (Brown, 2008). Moreover, assessment for learners is the factor that gives educators more

information about students learning and informs students what they have learnt during the learning process.

These situations are referred to as assessments to assist learning, or the formative use of assessment (see e.g., Black & Wiliam, 1998; Wiliam, 2007). Assessment of school provides with information that supports not only educators, but also administrators, policymakers, students, parents and researchers assess the state students learning and make decisions about consequences and actions. The clear objectives of the assessment are an important factor at all stages of its development.

More specifically, Hattie and Timperley (2007) defined assessment as “activity used to assess students“level of proficiency” (p. 101). Therefore, assessment can be grouped into formative and summative goals. Formative assessment aims to improve learning and is conducted during the learning process involving feedback to inform students’ performance. The latter type of assessment (summative), which aims to certify student learning, is conducted at the end of a learning period and involves scoring and grading. Assessment of learning in education assists not only teachers to evaluate and determine their students knowledge, but also students to calculate their achievements and improve their performance on education during learning process. It gives more chance to work on themselves and open new horizons by enhancing outlook.

Lessons from these studies suggest a gap between interpretations of assessment in English speaking countries and non-English speaking countries and signify that the culture in different sites may contribute to dissimilar conceptions and practice of assessment. In response, Brown et al. (2009) have suggested that to be effective, a policy initiator should identify and respond to teachers’ conceptions before implementing new plans for educational reform. Cultural factors may hold particular relevance given that assessment values among Confucian peoples and European countries may differ from those held in the West

(Kennedy et al., 2008).

Indeed, there are many reasons why schools and teachers should establish AFL in education properly. Teachers can get ensuring all children achieve high standards, identifying areas where improvement is needed, monitoring students knowledge regularly and providing effectiveness of teaching.

Instructors often conflate assessment with grading. This is a mistake. It must be understood that student assessment is more than just grading. Remember that assessment links student performance to specific learning objectives in order to provide useful information to instructors and students about student achievement. Traditional grading on the other hand, according to Stassen et al. does not provide the level of detailed and specific information essential to link student performance with improvement. “Because grades don’t tell you about student performance on individual (or specific) learning goals or outcomes, they provide little information on the overall success of your course in helping students to attain the specific and distinct learning objectives of interest.” (Stassen et al., 2001, pg. 6) Instructors, therefore, must always remember that grading is an aspect of student assessment but does not constitute its totality.

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